

CONVERSION OF FIBRE TO YARN.

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Abstract: Textile production up until the seventeenth century was predominantly a specialised domestic production system (cottage industry) mainly done by women. The key fibres used were wool, cotton, silk, hemp and flax (for linen). The advent of the Industrial Revolution meant mechanisation of the production process, allowing new and much faster methods of manufacturing to emerge. Over the next 300 years, it would be both developments in processing and advances in engineered fibres that would change the textile landscape. Whilst the first man-made or manufactured fibres, namely regenerated cellulose fibres, were developed in the late nineteenth century, industrial production of these fibres only really started in the early twentieth century.

Key words: Fiber, lint, cotton, ginning, cotton seeds, staple yarns, combed cotton, carded cotton, synthetic and blends, worsted, woollen, the classification of yarns.

INTRODUCTION.The term yarn may be defined as a linear collection of filaments or fibres in a twisted state or bound by other means, and possessing good tensile strength and elasticity properties. From the various types of commercially manufactured yarns, it may be seen that there are a great many functional and design possibilities. Fibres are processed in both pure and blended states. Considerable variation in yarn is made from a particular fibre or filament is possible. The classification of yarns (Table 1) is based on their physical characteristics as well as performance properties.

Staple yarns are defined as assembled strands of fibres twisted together to form a continuous strand according to the properties required. There are four staple-yarn manufacturing systems commercially available. These are carded, combed, woollen and worsted systems. Synthetic and regenerated fibres are stapled and treated like natural fibre (cotton or wool) with different fibre lengths, diameters and crimps, which enables processing to be carried out with few difficulties.

Table 1 Yarn types and their properties

Yarn type	General yarn properties
Staple yarns	Good hand, cover, comfort and textured appearance Average strength and uniformity
Combed cotton	
Carded cotton	
Synthetic and blends	
Worsted	
Woollen	
Continuous-filament yarns	High strength, uniformity and possibility for very fine yarns Fair hand and poor covering power
Natural Man-made or synthetic	
Novelty yarns	Decorative features and characteristics
Fancy	
Metallic	
Industrial yarns	Functional; designed and produced to satisfy a specific set of requirements
Tyre cord	
Rubber or elastic core	
Multiply coated	
High-bulk yarns	
Staple	Great covering power with less weight, high loftiness or fullness
Continuous filament (Taslan)	
Stretch yarns	High stretchability and cling without high pressure, good handle and covering power
Twist-heat set-untwist	
Crimp heat-set	
Stress under tension	
Knit-deknit	
Gear crimp	

Silk was the first natural continuous-filament yarn in use before the introduction of man-made fibres. Man-made filaments are manufactured by extruding polymer

solution through a spinneret, at which point the solution solidifies by coagulation, cooling or evaporation. The number of orifices in the spinneret dictates the number of filament in the bundle. The diameter and amount of drawing provided will subsequently decide the diameter of the filament. The filaments are cut and crimped according to the required length for conversion to staple fibre, which will undergo further staple-yarn production.

These are designed and produced for decorative purposes and are seldom used to make an entire fabric, except in drapery applications. Most novelty yarns are of the fancy or metallic type. Fancy yarns are generally produced by the irregular plying of staple fibre or continuous filaments and are characterised by the presence of abrupt and periodic effects. The periodicity of these effects may be irregular or constant. The novelty effect is brought about by a programmed difference in twist level or input rate in one or more components during the plying of the yarns. This results in differential bending or wrapping between the components or in segments of buckled yarn that are permanently entangled in the composite yarn structure.

Industrial design requires special end-use yarns with specific functional characteristics. These yarns are engineered for performance under specified conditions. Many industrial yarns do not have the visual and tactile properties of yarns used for apparel and home-furnishing applications. Examples are tyre cord, asbestos and glass yarns, twine, rubber or elastic threads, core-spun yarns, wire yarn, sewing thread, heavy monofilaments and split-film yarns.

A high-bulk yarn may be a staple or continuous-filament yarn with normal extensibility but an unusually high level of loftiness or fullness. These yarns retain bulkiness in both relaxed and stressed conditions. High covering power with lesser weight is possible in fabrics made of high-bulk yar.

Textured yarns preset for high extensibility are termed stretch yarns. While most can be stretched up to twice their normal or relaxed length, some can be stretched up to even three or four times their relaxed length. These yarns are highly extensible and highly elastic. Most stretch yarns are produced by texturising thermoplastic

continuous-filament yarns. This results in reasonably good nonlinearity or crimp in the individual filaments. The nonlinear structure of the filaments is heat-set but not entangled as in the case of the high-bulk yarns.

A staple-spun yarn is a linear assembly of fibres, usually held together by the insertion of twist, to form a continuous strand that is smaller in cross-section but of a particular specified length. It is used for making fabrics in processes such as knitting, weaving and sewing. The amount of strength or the quality of handle and appearance will depend on the way the fibres are assembled in the yarn system. The fibres can be natural or man-made. Man-made staple-fibre yarns are manufactured by using staple fibre cut from continuous filament before spinning. Staple-fibre yarns can be subdivided and classified on the basis of fibre length, spinning method and yarn construction. Each of these categories can be further subdivided. Staple-spun yarn can be classified as either short staple or long staple. A staple fibre has a length of between 10 and 500mm. Short staple fibre has a maximum length of 60mm (cotton fibre is a short staple at about 25–45mm). Long staple fibre has a length of more than 60mm (wool fibre is a long staple at about 60–150mm).

Different spinning methods are available in making yarns, including ring-spun, rotor-spun, twistless, wrap-spun and core-spun yarns.

-Ring-spun yarns: This is the most widely used method of staple-fibre yarn production. The fibres are twisted around each other to give strength to the yarn.

-Rotor-spun yarns: These are similar to ring-spun yarns and usually made from short staple fibres. They produce a more regular and smoother, though weaker, yarn than ring spinning.

- Twistless yarns: The fibres are held together by adhesives, not by the twist, and are often laid over a continuous filament core.

- Wrap-spun yarns: These yarns are made from staple fibres bound by another yarn, which is usually a continuous man-made filament yarn. The yarns can be made from either short or long staple fibres.

- Core-spun yarns: Core-spun yarns have a central core that is wrapped with staple fibres, and are produced in a single operation at the time of spinning. For example, a cotton sheath for handle and comfort, with a filament (often polyester) core for added strength; or cotton over an elastomeric core.

There are a number of operations. - Mixing: The term 'mixing' refers to the bringing together of more than one variety of the same basic fibre. For example, Egyptian cotton fibre can be combined with American cotton fibre and the final yarn remains 100% cotton.

- Blending: Blending refers to the bringing together of fibres of different types. For example, wool and silk or cotton and polyester fibres.

- Cleaning and fibre separation: Bales of raw fibres contain a variety of impurities, which must be removed. The first process divides and splits the bales into loose bunches of fibres of diminishing size to remove dust, seeds and other debris. Some fibre types are then washed or scoured and others can be combed or carded to further separate and clean the fibres.

- Fibre alignment: This process follows carding and combing. Several slivers or groups of carded or combed fibres are combined and attenuated to form a single sliver of straightened fibres. This process is known as drawing.

- Drafting and twisting: Drafting is the process of gently stretching out the slivers to reduce their linear density or thickness. The exact method and machinery used will depend upon the required yarn quality and count. In the final process, the required amount of twist is inserted into the single yarn.

The major aspect of yarn structure is its visual appearance, which is determined by the peripheral layer of fibres. The second aspect is its internal structure. Yarn structures are very variable. The differences are caused partly deliberately, according to the intended use of the yarn, but for the most part they are predetermined by the means available. For example, it is difficult to produce a yarn having properties similar to a ring-spun yarn by new spinning processes, and ring-spun yarn still represents the standard reference for comparison (Table 2). Yarn structure depends primarily upon

the properties of the raw materials, the spinning process and parameters, the spinning unit conditions, machine parameters and settings and twist levels, and so on. The yarn structure can be open or closed; bulky or compact; smooth, rough or hairy; soft or hard; circular or flat; thin or thick, and so on.

Table 2 Yarn structures from different spinning methods

	Ring-spun yarn		Open-end yarn		Air-jet yarn		Wrap yarn
	Classic	Compact	Rotor spun	Friction spun	Jet spun, two nozzles, false twist process	Vortex spun, one nozzle	Filament wrapped
Fibre deposition							
In the core	Parallel, helical	Parallel, helical	Less parallel, helical	Less parallel, helical	Parallel w/o twist	Parallel w/o twist	Parallel w/o twist
In the sheath	Parallel, helical	Parallel, helical	More random, less twisted	Less parallel, helical	6% of fibres twisted around the core in spirals	20% of fibres twisted around core in spirals	Filament windings
Fibre orientation							
Parallelism	Good	Very good	Medium	Low	Medium	Good	Very good
Compactness	Compact	Very compact; round	Open	Compact to open	Compact	Compact	Compact
Handle	Soft	Soft	Hard	Hard	Hard	Medium to hard	Soft
Hairiness	Noticeable	Low	Very low	Low	Some	Low to medium	Very low
Stiffness	Low	Low	High	High	High	Fairly high	Low

Figure 1 Application chart for staple spun yarns.

In addition to appearance, yarn structure also influences the following: handle; strength; elongation; insulating capacity; covering power; ability to resist wear, damage, strains, and so on; abrasion resistance; dyeability; tendency towards longitudinal bunching of fibres; and wearing comfort, and so on.

Figure 1 shows the count range for the different end-uses of staple-fibre yarns. In addition to the very fine yarn count range of 2–7.5 tex meant for hosiery, staple-fibre yarns have almost similar market areas, where fine to medium yarn counts of 7.5–40tex are largely used to make textiles for clothing and apparel. Spun staple yarns hold a major position in the market for items such as shirts, blouses, home textiles, bed linen, trousers and suits.

Filament yarns a filament yarn is a collection of parallel bundles of filaments lying close together along the whole length of the yarn. Man-made yarns are made by

extruding the required number of filaments in a single operation at the desired linear density. Yarns with only one filament are known as monofilaments and those with more than one filament are known as multifilaments.

Most synthetic fibres are extruded using polymers derived from by-products of petroleum and natural gas, which include polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and nylon as well as compounds such as acrylics, polyurethanes and polypropylene. The polymers are first converted from solid to fluid state by means of melting, dissolving using solvent, and so on. The fluid polymer is then extruded through a spinneret to convert the solution into filaments. There are four major types of synthetic fibre production techniques: Dry Spinning, Wet Spinning, melt spinning and gel spinning.

The spinneret is a metal component having one to several hundred small holes. The fluid polymer is injected through these tiny openings to produce filaments from polymer solution. This process of extrusion and solidification of innumerable filaments is known as the spinning of polymers. There are two types of extrusion: single-screw and twin-screw extrusion.

-Single screw-extrusion: This is one of the elementary tasks of polymer processing. The singlescrew extrusion process builds pressure on a polymer melt and forces it through a die or injects it into a mould. Most single-screw extrusion machines are plasticating, taking solids in pellet or powder form and melting them while simultaneously building pressure.

-Twin-screw extrusion: This is commonly used for mixing, compounding or reacting polymeric materials. The flexibility of the twin-screw extrusion tool allows the operation to be designed specifically for the formulation being processed. For example, the two screws may be co-rotating or counter-rotating, inter-meshing or non-inter-meshing. The design and configuration of the screws themselves may also be changed using forward conveying elements, reverse conveying elements, kneading blocks, and other designs that can assist in obtaining particular mixing characteristics.

Polymer spinning processes. There are a number of spinning processes.

-Wet spinning: Of the four processes, the oldest is wet spinning, as shown in Figure 2. This is used for polymers that need to be dissolved in a solvent before they can be spun. The spinneret remains submerged in a chemical bath, which causes the polymer to precipitate and then solidify as it emerges from the spinneret holes. (The name of the process is derived from the use of this ‘wet’ bath.) Acrylic fibre, Rayon fibre, Aramid fibre, Modacrylic fibre and Spandex fibres are all manufactured by the wet spinning process.

Figure 2 Schematic of wet-spinning process.

Dry spinning: Dry spinning is used for polymers that need to be dissolved in a solvent. However, solidification is obtained from evaporation of the solvent. After the polymer is dissolved in a volatile solvent, the solution is pumped through a spinneret. As the fibres emerge from the spinneret, air or inert gas is used to evaporate the solvent from the fibre. This results in solidification of the fibres, which can then be collected on a take-up wheel. The fibres are drawn to provide orientation to the polymer chains along the fibre axis. This technique is used only for polymers that cannot be melt-spun due to the safety and environmental concerns associated with solvent handling. Dry

spinning may be used for manufacturing acetate fibre, triacetate fibre, acrylic fibre, modacrylic fibre, PBI, Spandex fibre and vinyon.

Figure 3. End-uses of filament yarns.

SUMMARY.

Different types of yarns from staple fibres and continuous filaments from both natural and synthesised materials are described in terms of their structures, properties and applications. Appropriate yarn structures and manufacturing technologies are selected for required applications and properties. Detailed definitions and manufacturing principles for different types of yarns (e.g. simple, ply, cord, fancy and core-spun) are provided. Particular emphasis is given to various types of fancy yarns, which are described with suitable diagrams and detailed explanations of their manufacturing methods. In the case of synthetic continuous-filament yarns, manufacturing methods including melt spinning, wet spinning, dry spinning and gel spinning techniques are explained and different forms of continuous-filament yarns are dealt with, such as flat yarns, textured yarns, bi-component yarns and split tape or film yarns. In case of staple-fibre yarns, manufacturing technologies including ring, rotor,

air-jet spinning and Vortex spinning are explained together with the type of yarn structures obtained from the respective technologies and their end-uses.

Go to the market and collect as many different yarns as possible. Try to identify the type of yarn according to the classification given in Table 1.

With the help of a sensitive weighing balance, calculate the linear density of these yarns in (i) English count, Ne and (ii) Tex and tabulate these values. Pick up one continuous filament yarn and another staple fibre yarn almost of equal linear density.

REFERENCES

1. Deopura, B. L., Alagirusamy, R., Gupta, B., & Joshi, M. (Eds.). (2008). *Polyesters and polyamides*. Cambridge: Woodhead Publishing.
2. *Fundamentals of spun yarn technology*. Boca Raton: CRC Press. Lawrence, C. A. (Ed.). (2010).
3. *Advances in yarn spinning technology*. Cornwall: Woodhead Publishing. Lord, P. R. (2003). *Hand book of yarn production: technology, science and economics* (pp. 184–211).
4. Cambridge: Woodhead Publishing. McIntyre, J. E. (Ed.). (2004). *Synthetic fibres nylon, polyester, acrylic, polyolefin*.
5. Kh. Akhmetxodjayev, M. Tojiboyev, O. Sarimsakov, Kh. Sharipov. The Mathematical Model of Seed Movement on a Concave Profile Rib. *Engineering*, 2020, 12, 216-227 <https://www.scirp.org/journal/eng> ISSN Online: 1947-394X ISSN Print: 1947-393
6. B. Mardonov, F. Ibrokhimov, Kh. Akhmetxodjayev, M. Tojiboyev, Kh. Sharipov. Theoretical Study of the Movement of Cotton Seed Flow along the Contour of the Rib. *Engineering*, 2021, 13, 526-535 <https://www.scirp.org/journal/eng> ISSN Online: 1947-394X ISSN Print: 1947-3931
7. Kh. Sharipov, K. Abdurakhimov, S. Mukhiddinov, F. Rustamova. Theoretical Study Of The Movement Of Single And Systemic Seeds Along The Grate Of A Saw Gin With A Concave Profile. *The American Journal of Engineering*

and Technology (ISSN – 2689-0984) Published: June 18, 2021 | Pages: 21-29 Doi:
<https://doi.org/10.37547/tajet/Volume03Issue06-05>

8.O. Sarimsakov, Kh. Yo'ldashev, S. Madumarov, Kh. Sharioiv. Investigation of separation of usable fibers added to contaminants during cleaning cotton. Journal of interdisciplinary innovations and scientific research in Uzbekistan, No. 8 Issue 8, 05/20/2022, 448-456 p

9. Sharibboy Ergashev, Khayrullo Sharipov, Olimjon Sarimsakov. **Improvement of the Process of Separation of Cotton Fiber from Seeds.** Engineering, 2022, 14, 567-577. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/eng> ISSN Online: 1947-394X ISSN Print: 1947-393

10. Kh. Akhmedkhodzhaev, M. Tadjibayev, Kh. Sharipov. The saw gin stand with adjustable movement of the roll box. Scientific Research Publishing, Engineering. USA, 2019